

**EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF TEACHER TRAINEES IN
RELATION TO GENDER AND SELF-EFFICACY**

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation was undertaken to study the emotional intelligence of teacher trainees in relation to gender and self-efficacy. The study was conducted with the help of descriptive research method. A representative sample of 693 teacher trainees was selected by employing incidental sampling technique. Emotional Intelligence Scale by Dr. S. K. Mangal and Shubhra Mangal and Self-Efficacy Scale by Dr. G. P. Mathur and Dr. Raj Kumari Bhatnagar were used to collect the necessary data. Descriptive statistics and Analysis of variance were used to analyze the data. The findings of the study indicated that male and female teacher trainees possessed similar level of emotional intelligence. Teacher trainees with different level of self-efficacy do not differ significantly in terms of their emotional intelligence. Gender and self-efficacy do not interact significantly with respect to emotional intelligence of teacher trainees.

KEYWORDS: Emotional Intelligence, Gender, Self-Efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

Emotional Intelligence is “the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves and for managing emotions effectively in others and ourselves”. Emotional Intelligence often measured as an Emotional Intelligence Quotient describes an ability, capacity, skill or (in the case of the trait EI model) a self-perceived ability, to identify, assess, and manage the emotions of one's self, of others, and of groups. It is a relatively new area of psychological research. The definition of EI is constantly changing. Emotional intelligence includes a broad array of sub-skills including how we monitor our own and others feelings and emotions, how we discriminate and assess and how we use this knowledge to guide our thinking and actions. It includes assertiveness, impulse control, adaptability, motivation and optimism. The earliest roots of emotional intelligence can be traced to Darwin's work on the importance of emotional expression for survival and second adaptation. In the 1900s, even though traditional definitions of intelligence emphasized cognitive aspects such as memory and problem-solving, several influential researchers in the intelligence field of study had begun to recognize the importance of the non-cognitive aspects. For instance, as early as 1920, E. L. Thorndike used the term social intelligence to describe the skill of understanding and managing other people. Similarly, in 1940 David Wechsler described the influence of non-intellective factors on intelligent behavior, and further argued that our models of intelligence would not be complete until we can adequately describe these factors. In 1983, Howard Gardner's Frames of Mind: The Theory of Multiple Intelligences introduced the idea of Multiple Intelligences which included both Interpersonal intelligence (the capacity to understand the intentions, motivations and desires of other people) and Intrapersonal intelligence (the capacity to understand oneself, to appreciate one's

feelings, fears and motivations). In Gardner's view, traditional types of intelligence, such as IQ, fail to fully explain cognitive ability. Thus, even though the names given to the concept varied, there was a common belief that traditional definitions of intelligence are lacking in ability to fully explain performance outcomes. Albert Bandura defined self-efficacy as "Beliefs in one's capabilities to organise and execute the courses of action required to produce given achievements". He hypothesized that the level of self-efficacy can be used to determine whether a task will be initiated, the amount of effort that will be expended and the level of persistence to complete the task when face with obstacles and aversive experiences. Once a person has acquired a high level of self-efficacy belief, he will become motivated to invest more effort in his life. Bandura theorized self-efficacy in his seminal articles; extensive studies were done to extend the role of self-efficacy as a mechanism to better understand behavioral change in the area of academic performance, cognitive functioning, health, promotion, athletic performance, career choices and coping with mental disorders. Self-efficacy is multidimensional, that is, domain specific or context dependent. This means that high sense of efficacy in a particular domain may not necessarily translate in to having similar level in another domain. Even within the same domain, there may be different levels of self-efficacy beliefs occurring in various contexts. Self-efficacy is important because it plays a role in how you feel about yourself and whether or not you successfully achieve your goals in life. Continue reading to learn more about this concept that is central to Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory, which emphasizes the role of observational learning, social experience, and reciprocal determinism in personality development. **Carter (2004)** revealed that students with more computer experience developed a higher self-efficacy and those with less computer experience had lower self-efficacy beliefs. **Sen and Sood (2016)** revealed that change proneness and self-efficacy are significantly and positively correlated. This means that the teachers with a tendency to accept new ideas, techniques in their teaching were more able to cope with their environment, realize their skills effectively and had a sense of higher self-efficacy. **Reena (2017)** concluded that female prospective teachers possessed significantly more computer self-efficacy as compared to male prospective teachers. Prospective secondary school teachers of science stream possessed significantly higher computer self-efficacy in comparison to the prospective teachers of arts stream. **Alam (2018)** showed that secondary school students differed significantly in terms of the nature of school and gender on emotional intelligence. Result further revealed in relation to area students did not differ significantly in their emotional intelligence. It was revealed by **Reena and Sood (2018)** that male and female prospective secondary school teachers differed significantly from each other with respect to their computer self-efficacy. Prospective secondary school teachers possessed average level of computer self-efficacy. **Ashraf (2020)** concluded that self-esteem, self-efficacy and emotional intelligence had a significant and positive relationship with the organizational commitment of private secondary school teachers. Self-esteem, emotional intelligence and self-efficacy were found to be the significant predictors of organizational commitment. **Kumar (2020)** found that higher secondary school students possessed average level of emotional intelligence. Female students were better than male students in terms of their emotional intelligence. **Puju (2021)** concluded that 18.25% boys of senior secondary schools have high-level of self-efficacy, 65.00% boys of senior secondary schools had average level of self-efficacy whereas 16.75% boys of senior secondary schools had low level of self-efficacy. Whereas 18.00% girls of senior secondary schools have high-level of self-efficacy, 65.75% girls of senior secondary schools have average level of self-efficacy whereas 16.25% girls of senior secondary schools had low level of self-efficacy.

It has been observed on the basis of the thorough review of the literature that very few studies are on emotional intelligence of teacher trainees with respect to gender and self-efficacy. Hence, it was decided to see the impact of gender and self-efficacy on emotional intelligence of teacher trainees.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the difference in emotional intelligence among teacher trainees with regard to their gender.
2. To study the difference in emotional intelligence among teacher trainees with regard to their level of self-efficacy.
3. To study the interactional effect of gender and level of self-efficacy with regard to emotional intelligence of teacher trainees.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence of teacher trainees with regard to their gender.
2. There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence of teacher trainees with regard to their level of self-efficacy.
3. There exists no significant interactional effect of gender and level of self-efficacy with regard to emotional intelligence of teacher trainees.

METHODOLOGY

Survey technique under descriptive research was used to achieve the objectives of the present study.

SAMPLING

In the present research, a representative sample of 693 teacher trainees were selected from teacher education institutions of Hamirpur, Kullu, Kangra and Mandi districts of Himachal Pradesh by applying incidental sampling technique.

RESEARCH TOOLS USED

Emotional Intelligence inventory by Dr. S. K. Mangal and Shubhra Mangal (2015) and Self-Efficacy Scale by Dr. G. P. Mathur and Dr. Raj Kumari Bhatnagar (2012) were used for collection of data.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF DATA

Descriptive statistics and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to analyze the data. Detail of the analysis is given below:

In order to study the main effect of gender and level of self-efficacy of emotional intelligence of teacher trainees along with their interactional effect, analysis of variance (2x3 factor design) involving two types of gender i.e. male and female and three level of self-efficacy i.e. high, average and low was applied on mean emotional intelligence scores. The mean emotional intelligence score of male and female teacher trainees with high average and low level of self-efficacy are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

MEAN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE SCORES OF TEACHER TRAINEES WITH RESPECT TO GENDER AND LEVEL OF SELF-EFFICACY

	Level of Self-Efficacy Gender		Mean Emotional Intelligence Scores			
			High Level	Average Level	Low Level	Total
1	Male (283)	Mean	123.26	123.907	122.41	124.01
		S.D.	17.466	17.983	17.978	18.046
		N	53	193	39	283
2	Female (410)	Mean	126.59	125.11	126.52	125.27
		S.D.	15.650	17.702	16.641	17.654
		N	52	292	64	410
3	Total (693)	Mean	124.91	124.631	125.17	124.75
		S.D.	16.597	17.806	19.161	17.813
		N	105	485	103	693

Afterwards, the statistical technique of Two-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied on mean emotional intelligence scores of male and female teacher trainees possessing high, average and low level of self-efficacy. The 'F' values were computed and results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2
SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS OF ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE FOR EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE SCORES OF TEACHER TRAINEES WITH RESPECT TO GENDER AND SELF-EFFICACY

S. No.	Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom(df)	Mean Square	F Ratio
1.	Gender (A)	168.023	1	168.023	0.527 ^{NS}
2.	Self- Efficacy B)	52.130	2	26.065	0.082 ^{NS}
3.	Gender* Self Efficacy (A*B)	201.1387	2	100.693	0.316 ^{NS}
4.	Error Variance	219071.176	687	318.881	
5.	Total	219568.805	692		

NS-Not Significant

1. MAIN EFFECTS

1. GENDER (A)

The calculated value of 'F' for the main effect of gender on emotional intelligence of teacher trainees, irrespective of their level of self-efficacy came out to be 0.527 which is less than the table value (3.85) even at 0.05 level of significance, for df 1 and 687. Hence, **Hypothesis No. 1** that “**There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence among teacher trainees with regard to their gender**”, was accepted. So, it may be interpreted that male and female teacher trainees didn't differ significantly from each other in term of their emotional intelligence. This is also evident from mean emotional intelligence score of male and female teacher trainees which come out to be 124.01 and 125.27 respectively. Although, the female teacher trainees had shown higher mean emotional intelligence scores (125.27) as compared to the male teacher trainees (124.01). However, the mean difference was not found to be statistically significance. Further, the calculated value of eta-squared (0.000765) indicated that gender has a very small effect on emotional intelligence of teacher trainees. In other words, it may be said that gender contributes only about 0.077 % towards emotional intelligence of teacher trainees. The mean emotional intelligence scores of male and female teacher trainees are shown in Figure 1 as follows:

FIGURE 1

MEAN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE SCORES OF MALE AND FEMALE TEACHER TRAINEES

2. SELF-EFFICACY (B)

The obtained value of 'F' for the main effect of self-efficacy on emotional intelligence of teacher trainees, irrespective of their gender, came out to be 0.082 which is less than the table value (3.00) even at 0.05 level of significance for df 2 and 687. Hence, **Hypothesis No. 2** that, “**There exists no significant difference in emotional intelligence among teacher trainees with regard to their level of self-efficacy**”, was accepted. So, it may be inferred

that teacher trainees belonging to different level of self-efficacy do not differ significantly from each other in term of their emotional intelligence. Although, the teacher trainees belonging to low level of self-efficacy had shown slightly higher mean of emotional intelligence scores (125.17) as compared to teacher trainees belonging to higher level of self-efficacy (124.91) and average level of self-efficacy (124.63). Further, the computed eta-squared (0.000237) indicated that self-efficacy has a very small effect on emotional intelligence of teacher trainees. In other words, it may be said that self-efficacy contributes only about 0.024 % towards emotional intelligence of teacher trainees. Figure 2 shows the mean emotional intelligence scores of teacher trainees with respect to level of self-efficacy.

FIGURE 2

MEAN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE SCORES OF TEACHER TRAINEES WITH RESPECT TO THEIR SELF-EFFICACY

3. INTERACTIONAL EFFECT (A X B)

The calculated value of ‘F’ for the interactional effect of gender and level of self-efficacy with respect to emotional intelligence of teacher trainees, came out to be 0.316 which is less than the table value (3.00) even at 0.05 level of significance for df 2 and 687. Hence, **Hypothesis No. 3** that, “**There exists no significant interactional effect of gender and level of self-efficacy on emotional intelligence of teacher trainees**”, was accepted.

Therefore, it may be interpreted that gender and self-efficacy taken together did not significantly influence the emotional intelligence of teacher trainees. Further, the computed eta-squared (0.000917) indicated that gender and self-efficacy (in a combined manner) has a very small combined effect on emotional intelligence of teacher trainees. In other words, it may be said that gender and self-efficacy (in a combined manner) contributes only about 0.092 % towards emotional intelligence of teacher trainees.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Male and female teacher trainees didn't differ significantly from each other in term of their emotional intelligence. This is also evident from mean emotional intelligence score of male and female teacher trainees which cone out to be 124.01 and 125.27 respectively. Although, the female teacher trainees had shown higher mean emotional intelligence scores (125.27) as compared to the male teacher trainees (124.01). However, the mean difference was not found to be statistically significance.
2. Teacher trainees belonging to different level of self-efficacy do not differ significantly from each other in term of their emotional intelligence. Although, the teacher trainees belonging to low level of self-efficacy had shown slightly higher mean of emotional intelligence scores (125.17) as compared to teacher trainees belonging to higher level of self-efficacy (124.91) and average level of self-efficacy (124.63).
3. Gender and self-efficacy taken together did not significantly influence the emotional intelligence of teacher trainees.

IMPLICATIONS

The present investigation was carried out to study the emotional intelligence of teacher trainees in relation to gender and self-efficacy. Findings revealed that Male and female teacher trainees didn't differ significantly from each other in term of their emotional intelligence. This is also evident from mean emotional intelligence score of male and female teacher trainees which cone out to be 124.01 and 125.27 respectively. Although, the female teacher trainees had shown higher mean emotional intelligence scores (125.27) as compared to the male teacher trainees (124.01). Teacher educators should make efforts to provide equal opportunities to teacher trainees without any discrimination on the basis of gender. Adult education programmes and occasional lectures on emotional intelligence should be organized time to time. It was suggested that such types of activities and programmes should be organized in the teacher education institutions so that the teacher trainees should become emotionally strong. They should express themselves independently. Further, it was found that teacher trainees belonging to different level of self-efficacy do not differ significantly from each other in term of their emotional intelligence. Although, the teacher trainees belonging to low level of self-efficacy had shown slightly higher mean of emotional intelligence scores (125.17) as compared to teacher trainees belonging to higher level of self-efficacy (124.91) and average level of self-efficacy (124.63). It was recommended that such type of co-curricular activities should be organized that can make student more efficient in their life. In order to raise efficacy among teacher trainees a conducive and convenient environment should be provided in the institutions as well as at home.

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